

A CASE STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HOMEOPATHIC MEDICINE IN CASE OF MOLLUSCUM CONTAGIOSUM

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Article Received on 05 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 05 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18884886>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. S. N. Sharma*¹, Namrata Singh Kushwaha², Siddhi Jain², Vikrant Rana², Sanskriti Mishra², Vandana Yadav². (2026). A Case Study on The Effectiveness of Homeopathic Medicine In Case of Molluscum Contagiosum. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(5), 1699–1704.

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ABSTRACT

Molluscum contagiosum (MC) is a common viral infectious dermatosis that primarily affects children and people with weakened immune systems. Firm, dome-shaped papules with glossy, umbilicated surfaces are clinically indicative of MC. MC is a self-limiting condition. **Case Summary:** 57-year-old female complaints of multiple firm rounds, shiny pinkish papular skin lesions on bilateral medial aspect of things which is aggravated by bathing and washing for 1 month. *SULPHUR IM CH Potency, 1 dose* was prescribed on the basis of totality of symptoms. The case was followed for two months, which showed complete resolution of MC lesion. This case suggests the effectiveness of individualized homoeopathic medicine in cases of MC.

KEYWORDS: Individualized homoeopathic medicine, Sulphur, Molluscum Contagiosum, Case Report.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prevalent skin disorders, Molluscum contagiosum is mostly seen in children and people with weakened immune systems. It is brought on by the Molluscum contagiosum

virus and spreads through direct contact with infected skin, either sexually or non-sexually. MC delivers clinically as dome-shaped, hard, pink, or skin-colored papules.^[1]

EPIDEMIOLOGY

A common skin infection that affects people of all ages worldwide, Molluscum Contagiosum (MC) is more common in youngsters, sexually active adults, and people with impaired immune systems.^[3]

In the general population, it makes up about 1% of all dermatological diagnoses; instances are more common in warm regions humid environments.^[4]

It has been discovered that MC is more common in tropical regions. The frequency of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is believed to be around 7% in immune-competent youngsters and up to 18% in adults.^[1]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The Molluscum Contagiosum Virus (MCV), a double-stranded DNA virus belonging to the Poxviridae family—more precisely, the Molluscipoxvirus genus—causes Molluscum Contagiosum (MC). The virus mainly affects keratinocytes in the epidermis, resulting in the development of distinctive papules that have a central umbilication and a dome shape.^[3]

- (1) Lesion formation and viral replication.
- (2) Mechanisms of immune evasion.
- (3) The host's immune reaction.

CLINICAL FEATURES

Clinical observations and the patient's medical history are used to diagnose MC. The diagnosis is aided by a dermatoscopy. Lesions will show up under dermatoscopy as firm, dome-shaped, skin-colored or pink papules with a central umbilication. They could show either as a linear distribution or in clusters.

While adults frequently show with lesions on the anogenital area, abdomen, and inner thighs as a result of sexual contact, children typically suffer with lesions on the face, torso, extremities, and axillary area. In atypical MC cases, histopathology is explored.^[2]

INVESTIGATIONS

Molluscum Contagiosum (MC) is mostly diagnosed clinically based on its distinctive umbilicated, dome-shaped papules. However, more testing might be required to confirm the diagnosis and rule out other illnesses in atypical, persistent, or immunocompromised patients.^[3]

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 57-year-old female patient, visited the outpatient department of Dr. M.P.K. Homoeopathic medical college, hospital and Research Centre, Jaipur on 25/07/2025 for the complaints of multiple firm, round, shiny, pinkish papular skin lesions on bilateral medial aspect of thighs which is aggravated by bathing and washing for 1 month.

She had not taken any treatment for the present complaint prior to consultation. There was no significant past medical history reported.

CLINICAL FINDING

On general examination, the patient was conscious, cooperative, and well oriented to time, place, and person. There were no signs of pallor, cyanosis, jaundice, clubbing, or lymphadenopathy.

Systemic examination did not reveal any abnormality.

DIAGNOSIS: Contagiosum Molluscum (ICD -11:1E7)

ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF SYMPTOMS

Mental General	Physical General	Particular General
-	T/R - Hot ²⁺ Thirst - small quantity in at short interval. ¹⁺ Desire -sweet. ²⁺	Multiple firm, round, shiny pinkish papular eruption on bilateral medial aspect of thigh with itching present < bathing, washing. ³⁺

REPERTORISATION

Remedy	Sulph	Sep	Calc	Rhus-t	Clem	Caust	Kali-c	Lyc	Merc	Mez
Totally	14	10	9	9	9	8	8	8	7	7
Symptoms Covered	5	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4
[Kent] [Skin]Eruptions:Itching:	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	3
[Kent] [Skin]Eruptions:Hard:	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
[Kent] [Skin]Eruptions:Papular:	2	2	2	0	0	2	2	1	2	0
[Kent] [Skin]Eruptions:Vesicular:Washing:Agg:	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1
[Kent] [Stomach]Desires:Sweets:	3	2	2	2	0	0	2	3	1	0
[Kent] [Generalities]Bathing:Agg:	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2

PRESCRIPTION

Sulphur 1M /1 Dose /EMES and Placebo /TDS for 7 Days were prescribed on 25/07/2025.

FOLLOW UP AND OUTCOME

Date	Follow up	Prescription
2/8/2025	Eruption better itching,	Placebo/ TDS for 7 days
8/8/2025	Better in warts<bathing	Placebo/ TDS for 15 days
25/8/2025	Better in complaints	Placebo/ TDS for 7 days
29/8/2025	Better, right side of thighs, left side eruption slightly increased.	Sulphur 1M/1Dose/ EMES Placebo/ TDS for 7 days
5/9/2025	Better in complaints, left side eruption better.	Placebo/ TDS for 15 days
19/9/2025	No eruption present.	Placebo/ TDS for 15 days
EMES= Early Morning Empty Stomach		

DISCUSSION

A frequent treatment for the viral skin infection Molluscum contagiosum is local destructive measures, which can be uncomfortable and recurrent. This case was treated successfully with Individualized homoeopathic medicine. *Sulphur 1M CH potency, 2 Doses, early morning empty stomach* were prescribed in 2 months intervals. As seen in previous research article (case report)⁵, it is seen that Sulphur acts better in cases of Molluscum Contagiosum when prescribed on the basis of totality of symptom as individualised medicine. The patient recovered without any aggravation or recurrence during the follow-up period.

CONCLUSION

This case report shows the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicine in case of molluscum contagiosum. However, the self-limiting nature of the Molluscum Contagiosum and the limitations of a single case report, definitive conclusions cannot be drawn. Thus, a Larger and well-designed controlled research studies are required to show the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicine in cases of molluscum contagiosum.

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PHOTOGRAPH

